

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING TELECOMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE INFORMATICS TEACHERS

Abdullayev Nozimjon Qodiraliyevich

2nd year basic doctoral student

Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan
named after Tashmukhammad Niyazovich Qori Niyazi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430232>

Abstract : This article is discussed about telecommunication technologies which is necessary and beneficial for future informatics teachers in their session.

Key words: approach, computer, method, science, technology, telecommunication, professional development.

Аннотация: В данной статье речь пойдет о телекоммуникационных технологиях, которые необходимы и полезны будущим учителям информатики на занятиях.

Ключевые слова: подход, компьютер, метод, наука, технология, телекоммуникации, повышение квалификации.

Today, computer science is recognized as a basic and general educational field aimed at developing students' skills related to the creation of information models. Since a large part of the educational materials is devoted to learning information technology, the learning process is characterized by rapid changes in training content and a continuous increase in qualification requirements for professionals. Against the background of the rapid development of information technology, the task of developing experts in the field of education in the field of computer science in universities of education is becoming more and more urgent.

Additionally, the requirements for specialized training for computer science teachers are constantly changing due to changes in the content of teaching materials and differences in presentation approaches. The professional training of a future informatics teacher at a pedagogical university meets the needs of the school related to the need for highly qualified specialists who are able to take an active part in the modernization of the educational process, using computer teaching aids and Internet resources in their work. There are many technology tools for making better for education, one of them is telecommunication.

Telecommunication, short for "telecommunications," refers to the transmission of information over a distance using electronic means. It involves

the exchange of data, voice, or video between individuals, devices, or systems. Telecommunication encompasses a wide range of technologies and methods, including:

1. *Wired Communication*: Transmission of signals through physical mediums such as cables and wires, including traditional telephone lines and fiber-optic cables.

2. *Wireless Communication*: Transmission of signals without the use of physical cables, utilizing technologies such as radio waves, microwaves, and satellite communication.

3. *Networking*: Interconnecting computers and other devices to enable communication and data exchange, often over the internet or private networks.

4. *Internet Communication*: Encompasses various online services, email, instant messaging, and other applications that facilitate communication over the internet.

5. *Telephony*: The technology of transmitting voice signals for audio communication, which can include traditional landline telephones or Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) systems.

6. *Video Conferencing*: Real-time visual communication between individuals or groups located in different places, often facilitated by internet-based platforms.

7. *Data Transmission*: Transfer of digital data between devices, including the internet, local networks, and other communication channels.

Telecommunication plays a crucial role in connecting people globally, facilitating business transactions, enabling remote education, and supporting various aspects of modern life. It is a broad field that continues to evolve with advancements in technology.

Telecommunication in education refers to the use of communication technologies to facilitate learning and educational activities over distances. This can include various tools and methods such as video conferencing, online platforms, and virtual classrooms. Telecommunication in education enables remote access to educational resources, interactive collaboration among students and teachers, and the delivery of courses and training beyond traditional physical classrooms. It plays a crucial role in distance learning, online education, and the creation of inclusive educational opportunities, breaking down geographical barriers for both students and educators.

Telecommunication technologies is vital in shaping the education of future informatics teachers. Virtual classrooms, online collaboration tools, and video

conferencing platforms enable remote learning, fostering a global community of educators. These technologies facilitate access to diverse resources, promote interactive teaching methods, and support ongoing professional development for aspiring informatics teachers. Additionally, real-time communication tools allow for mentorship and knowledge exchange, enhancing the overall quality of education in the field.

Telecommunication technologies in education for future informatics teachers are essential for several reasons. Firstly, they enable access to a wealth of online resources, keeping educators abreast of the latest developments and ensuring a comprehensive understanding of computer science concepts.

Secondly, these technologies facilitate collaborative learning by providing platforms for real-time communication and teamwork, preparing future teachers for the collaborative nature of the tech industry.

Moreover, telecommunication tools support remote teaching, allowing for flexibility and inclusivity, especially beneficial in reaching aspiring computer science educators in various locations or with different schedules.

Overall, the integration of telecommunication technologies enriches the education of future informatics teachers, offering them dynamic, interconnected, and adaptable learning experiences.

Addressing the preparation of future informatics teachers for telecommunication education requires a strategic pedagogical approach. Integrating real-world case studies, hands-on projects, and industry collaboration can enhance their practical skills and adaptability to evolving technologies. Continuous professional development, staying abreast of industry trends, and fostering a problem-solving mindset are crucial elements in addressing this urgent pedagogical challenge.

It is known that there are some advantages and disadvantages of using telecommunication technologies in education. Telecommunications in lessons can be highly useful for several reasons:

1. **Enhanced Access to Information:** Telecommunications enable access to a vast array of information, resources, and experts, enriching the learning experience.

2. **Interactive Learning:** It facilitates interactive and collaborative learning experiences, allowing students to engage with course materials in dynamic ways.

3. **Flexibility:** Telecommunications provide flexibility in scheduling and learning pace, accommodating diverse student needs and preferences.

4. **Global Perspective:** It connects students with a global audience, fostering cultural exchange and a broader understanding of different perspectives.

5. **Adaptability to Various Learning Styles:** Through multimedia elements, virtual simulations, and diverse online content, telecommunications cater to different learning styles.

6. **Cost-Efficiency:** It can reduce costs associated with traditional classroom setups, making education more affordable for both institutions and students.

7. **Real-Time Communication:** Instant communication tools facilitate real-time interaction between students and instructors, promoting quicker feedback and clarification.

However, it's crucial to note that the effectiveness of telecommunications in lessons depends on proper implementation, technological infrastructure, and consideration of individual learning needs. Balancing online and traditional teaching methods is often key to creating a well-rounded educational experience. Teachers also reported a number of factors that influenced the success of student-based telecommunications activities. When teachers use networks to implement classroom exchange projects, progressive planning and full cooperation among participating teachers are likely to be critical to the success of the project. The content and scope of the activities as well as the goals and objectives of the project must be precisely defined. Also, as with any technology project aimed at supporting and enhancing student learning, the relevance of communication activities to the teacher's ongoing curriculum is important.

It is mentioned above that several pedagogical problems may arise for informatics teachers using telecommunications in education. They are:

1. **Technology Barriers:** Teachers may encounter challenges related to technical issues, such as poor internet connectivity, software glitches, or hardware limitations, disrupting the flow of the lesson.

2. **Digital Literacy Gaps:** Students and teachers may have varying levels of digital literacy, leading to disparities in their ability to navigate online platforms and utilize telecommunication tools effectively.

3. **Engagement and Interaction:** Sustaining student engagement and fostering meaningful interaction in virtual classrooms can be challenging, as the absence of face-to-face communication may impact participation.

4. *Assessment Issues*: Designing fair and effective assessments in an online environment poses challenges, including concerns about cheating, the authenticity of student work, and the limitations of traditional testing methods.

5. *Inclusive Education*: Ensuring inclusivity for students with diverse learning needs can be complex in online settings, requiring teachers to adapt materials and activities to accommodate various learning styles and abilities.

6. *Lack of Physical Presence*: The absence of physical presence may hinder teachers' ability to observe non-verbal cues and provide immediate feedback, impacting their understanding of students' comprehension and engagement levels.

7. *Time Management*: Balancing synchronous and asynchronous activities, managing time effectively in virtual classrooms, and coordinating schedules across different time zones can be demanding for both teachers and students.

8. *Pedagogical Adaptation*: Adapting traditional teaching methods to an online format may require a significant adjustment, as certain instructional strategies may be less effective in a virtual setting.

9. *Security and Privacy Concerns*: Teachers may need to address concerns related to the security and privacy of online learning environments, including safeguarding student data and maintaining a secure online space.

10. *Professional Development Needs*: Keeping pace with evolving telecommunication technologies and refining pedagogical skills for online teaching requires ongoing professional development, which may pose a time and resource challenge for educators.

Addressing these pedagogical challenges involves a combination of training, support, and the development of strategies that cater to the unique dynamics of online education in the informatics field.

In order to ensure that future informatics teachers are involved in the process of developing new approaches to solving educational and pedagogical problems that involve the intra-system and inter-system transfer of knowledge and skills to new situations, it is necessary to use contemporary trends in preparing them for professional activities. Over the last three years, there has been a significant shift in education, primarily due to the pandemic's severe effects on people's schooling, particularly children. The new, emerging technologies, which were thought to be communication hurdles and for which people should become knowledgeable about them, caused the concept of education to erode.

References:

1. Богомолова Е.В. Методология непрерывной профессиональной

2. подготовки учителя информатики к комплексному использованию лично-ориентированного и синергетического подходов- Тамбов, 2011.
3. Council of the European Union. Conclusions on effective teacher education. Presented at Education, Youth, Culture and Sport Council meeting, 2014. URL: http://www.consilium.europa.eu/uedocs/cms_data/docs/press_data/en/educ/142690.pdf (retrieved on 10th May, 2016)
4. Farisi M.I. Developing the 21st-century social studies skills through technology integration // Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE, 2016. - 1(17).
6. Ибрагимов И.М. Информационные технологии и средства дистанционного обучения: учеб. пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений /Ильдар Муратович Ибрагимов; Под ред. А.Н. Ковшова. - М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2005.
7. Гриншкун В.В. Развитие интегративных подходов к созданию средств информатизации образования: автореф. ... док. пед. наук: 13.00.02. - Москва, 2004.
- 8.